

DELAMINATION ARREST FASTENERS IN AIRCRAFT COMPOSITE STRUCTURES

K. Y. Lin^{1*}, L. Richard¹, W. Liu¹

¹ Department of Aeronautics and Astronautics, University of Washington, Seattle, USA

* Corresponding author (lin@aa.washington.edu)

Keywords: *delamination, fastener, composite, mixed-mode fracture, aircraft structures*

1 Introduction

Carbon/epoxy composites are being used in primary aircraft structures to improve performance and save weight. However, carbon/epoxy materials are brittle and thus susceptible to impact damage which can cause multiple delaminations. In traditional metallic structures, the critical damage type is fatigue cracking, which is managed by damage tolerance methodology and arrested by tear straps. In laminated composites, the critical damage type is delamination. Damage tolerance methodology for metallic structures is not directly applicable because delamination damage is primarily driven by unpredictable discrete events, not by cyclic loading; while tear straps are simply ineffective in arresting delamination. Currently, crack arrest fasteners are being employed throughout the structure to address this type of damage. The goal is to provide fail-safety by stopping any propagating cracks as they reach the fastener, thus limiting the extent of the damage. At present, there is no analytical tool available for the proper sizing and optimization of these fastener features. In order to validate the design, large scale experiments are conducted to empirically determine if the fastener could arrest a propagating crack under a limited set of load cases; still, such validation exercise only produce a yes/no outcome, which are not beneficial for the optimization of future designs. Current practice often calls for one or two arrest fasteners installed in series. The lack of understanding of delamination propagation characteristics and the inability to optimize the crack arrest feature lead to weight penalties that could otherwise be avoided.

The present research is aimed squarely at solving the above problem. The research has yielded critical understandings of the underlying mechanisms of the arrest feature. An analytical tool for analyzing the

effectiveness of such feature has been developed, combining structural analysis, joint analysis, and fracture mechanics. It is determined that the elimination of mode I fracture component, the fastener joint stiffness [3], and the crack-face friction, are the three primary mechanisms with which the fastener arrests delaminations. In addition, experimental studies have been conducted to validate the analytical predictions. Good agreement between the analysis and experiment is observed.

2 Problem Description

The problem has been simplified to an infinite-width split-beam with fasteners attached at prescribed locations. Each beam thus is representative of either a delaminated sub-laminate or sub-component post-failure. When bonded, the two beams act as one, but as the crack propagates, the fastener is loaded and resists the propagation, with the ultimate goal of preventing excessive crack propagation below the critical loads for other failure modes. A schematic of the model near the fastener is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Schematic of the Split-beam Model

3 Modeling

A 2-D model of the system was created in the commercial software ABAQUS, shown in Figure 2, approximating an infinite width panel using plane strain elements to create a split-beam with a fastener modeled as two springs. Crack propagation is

simulated using the virtual crack closure technique (VCCT). A mixed-mode fracture law, B-K law, is used to determine crack propagation behavior. [2].

Figure 2. A 2-D Finite Element Model

The model consists of two 24-ply plates; with each 0.0075 inch thick ply represented by one element through the thickness and properties based on T800/3900 material properties. The CPE4R 2-D 4-node bilinear quadrilateral plane strain element with reduced integration is used in the plates.

The fastener is made of titanium with $E=16.5\text{msi}$. The modeling of the fastener is simplified to two independent springs: the axial property of the fastener is calculated assuming it is a constant diameter bar; while the shear stiffness is modeled using the fastener flexibility approach proposed by Huth [3] shown in Eq. (1). For single lap bolted graphite/epoxy joints, the constants are $a=2/3$, $b=4.2$ and $n=1$. A nonlinear spring is used to model the preload due to fastener install torque.

$$C = \left(\frac{t_1 + t_2}{2d} \right)^a \frac{b}{n} \left(\frac{1}{t_1 E_1} + \frac{1}{nt_2 E_2} + \frac{1}{2t_1 E_3} + \frac{1}{2nt_2 E_3} \right) \quad (1)$$

The disbond/delamination is assumed to propagate in a self-similar fashion, thus the crack tip always remains at the prescribed interface between the two plates regardless of load conditions. The simulation starts with the nodes tied together, and the FEA solver iterates to yield a load magnitude which satisfies the energy release rates required for crack propagation. The tie constraint of the crack tip node is then released, and the next node along the interface becomes the crack tip.

In general, the failure envelope should include many competing failure modes, such as tension failure, bending failure, fastener shear-off, fastener pull-through, etc. However, for the purpose of this study, only static crack propagation is considered. [2].

4 Experimental Studies

A novel delamination arrest experiment (Figure 3) has been designed and conducted to validate the analysis tool. Carbon/epoxy pre-preg tape with a quasi-isotropic layup, $((0/45/90/-45)_{3S}/\text{crack})_S$ has been tested. An initial crack is implanted at the mid-plane of the specimens using a teflon insert. A titanium fastener of 0.25 inches in diameter is used and tightened to a prescribed torque.

Figure 3. Two-Plate Crack Arrest Specimen

In order to capture the general influence of the installation torque on the crack propagation load, the installation torque was varied from “finger tight,” where the fastener could no longer be rotated by hand, to 47 in-lb. The maximum tested torque is approximately one half the factory install torque for the fasteners, and is representative of the minimum expected fastener torque in service.

The specimens were tested in tension with the crack tip tracked visually. The specimen was painted white to enhance the crack tip visibility and a 0.125 inch scale was marked on the side.

5 Results and Discussion

Results from the single-fastener specimen tests along with the analytical prediction showed that a fastener in the presence of the crack front retard the growth of the crack effectively, as seen in Figure 4. The fastener is located at crack-tip location zero. Prior to the fastener, the crack propagation is unstable, as seen by the dashed lines leading up to 0.125 inches before the fastener. At this stage, the crack tip is under mixed mode condition, but dominated by Mode I. If there were no arrest feature installed, this indicates that the crack propagation is totally unstable, with no opportunity for arrest.

In order to propagate the crack tip past the arrest fastener, the load must increase by at least 3.5 kip (37.5%). Increasing fastener install torque, which generates higher crack-face contact friction, leads to further increase in arrest capability. This represents a dramatic increase in load margin for this failure mode, demonstrating the effectiveness of the arrest

fastener. The analytical model predicts the propagation loads after the crack tip reaches the fastener. Different friction coefficients are used assuming a fastener preload equal to 50% of the tensile yield strength. The model diverges from the experimental results as crack length increases. This is because as the fastener joint becomes highly loaded, fastener rotation and bearing damage at the hole generate nonlinearities that are not accounted for in the analytical joint model.

Fig.4. Experimental Results and Predictions

Figure 5 shows the ABAQUS results for the case of pure Mode I loading. The fastener is positioned at crack-tip location zero. It can be seen clearly that the growth of the crack in Mode I loading is extremely well arrested by fastener. The crack stops within one fastener diameter from its location.

Fig. 5. Crack Propagation for Pure Mode I Loading

Additionally, further analysis shows that strong crack-face friction generated by fastener preload has a significant effect on crack arrest; however, fastener-hole clearance could limit the performance of the arrest mechanism by delaying the engagement

of the fastener joint. This is seen in Figure 4, where the black lines represent differing assumed coefficients of friction, and by increasing the frictional force; the propagation load was subsequently increased.

Figure 6 shows the energy release rate (ERR) components vs. crack-tip location. It can be seen that Mode I ERR is almost completely shut down by the fastener as the crack approaches the fastener. In this case, the G_I component is absorbed by the fastener and subsequently G_{II} must be increased to make up for the loss of G_I . In addition, since G_{IIC} is generally much higher than G_{IC} , by forcing the crack to propagate in pure Mode II, the crack propagation load is significantly increased.

Figure 6. ERR Components vs. Crack-Tip Location

6 Conclusion

The effectiveness of fasteners as a crack arrest feature in composite structures has been analyzed and experimentally verified. In the split-beam FEA model, in conjunction with the experimental testing, it is shown that the presence of a fastener is highly effective in arresting the propagation of a crack by two primary mechanisms: 1). its ability to restrict crack propagation to Mode II and 2). its elastic influence on the structure. It is shown that the fastener is extremely effective in eliminating G_I by restricting the opening displacement around the crack tip, forcing the crack into pure Mode II propagation. The propagation load subsequently increases, achieving the desired effect of crack arrestment, with the largest benefit seen in structures where the load conditions predominantly in a Mode I ERR component at the crack tip. In general, the

presence of a fastener will turn a potentially catastrophic unstable crack propagation into a stable one, providing fail-safety to the structure.

A two dimensional finite element modeling method has been developed. Although the experimental results generally agree with the analytical prediction; inaccuracies regarding the fastener joint modeling reduce agreement, which prompts for more research to understand this important part of the arrest feature. Specifically, traditional fastener flexibility approaches, used for bearing-bypass analysis of arrayed bolted/riveted-joints, provide inaccurate descriptions of the behavior of the fastener joint in an arrest configuration.

Also, there exists a deficit in the understanding and certainty of some parameters with significant influence on the arrest capability of the fasteners, such as the crack-face friction generated by fastener preload and fastener hole clearance.

Furthermore, other failure modes, including laminate failure, fastener yield, fastener pull-through and joint bearing failure, are not considered in this study. A proper design of such crack arrest mechanism should take into account all other failure modes.

In particular, further research is required to increase the certainty of the parameters needed to fully characterize the relationship of the installation torque of the fastener to the arrest effectiveness. The installation torque cannot be reliably related to the generated bearing pressure without experimental characterization of the fastener in question. As well, the crack face friction remains an area of further study. As these parameters are more fully understood, it is expected that the model and experimental results will converge.

Acknowledgment

This work was jointly sponsored by the U.S. Federal Aviation Administration, The Boeing Company, and Toray Composites. Their supports are greatly appreciated.

References

- [1] Cheung, C.H., Gray, P.G., and Lin, K.Y., "Fastener as Fail-Safe Disbond/Delamination Arrest for Laminated Composite Structures," Proc. of the 18th International Conference on Composite Materials, Jeju Island, Korea, August 21-26, 2011.
- [2] Cheung, C.H., and Lin, K. Y., "Numerical Analysis of Fastener Delamination/Disbond Arrest Mechanism in Aircraft Composite Structures," *Journal of aircraft*, Vol. 49, March 2012.
- [3] H. Huth "Influence of Fastener Flexibility on the Prediction of Load Transfer and Fatigue Life for Multiple-Row Joints," *Fatigue in Mechanically Fastened Composite and Metallic Joints, ASTM STP 927*, 1986, pp. 221-250.
- [4] G. Mabson, L. Deobald and B. Dopker "Fracture Interface Elements for the Implementation of the Virtual Crack Closure Technique," *Proceedings of 48th AIAA/ASME/ASCE/AHS/ASC Structures, Structural Dynamics, and Materials Conference*, Honolulu, Hawaii, Apr. 2007.